

WAYS TO EDUCATE STUDENTS ABOUT THE EVIL OF BULLYING IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract. *In this article, I am going to share my knowledge and opinion on bullying at schools. Also, I intend to write about the methods to explain this phenomenon to pupils in order they do not get psychologically and physically get hurt from bullying. I hope this will be helpful resource for teachers and pupils as this phenomenon has expanded in all means at most schools and other educational institutions.*

Keywords: *bullying, pedagogical problem, aggressive actions, victim, behavior, cyberbullying.*

СПОСОБЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ О ВРЕДЕ ХУЛИГАНСТВА НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В этой статье я поделюсь своими знаниями и мнением о травле в школах. Также я намерен написать о методах объяснения этого явления школьникам, чтобы они не пострадали психологически и физически от буллинга. Я надеюсь, что это будет полезным ресурсом для учителей и учеников, так как это явление широко распространено в большинстве школ и других учебных заведений.*

Ключевые слова: *буллинг, педагогическая проблема, агрессивные действия, жертва, поведение, кибербуллинг.*

Firstly, we will give general idea about bullying to the pupils so that they understand the basic features of bullying and bullying pupils.

The English word bullying means intimidation, physical or psychological terror aimed at causing fear in another and thereby subjugating him to himself. Previously, it was just an everyday concept, but in the last 20 years it has become an international socio-psychological and pedagogical term, behind which there is a whole set of social, psychological and pedagogical problems. As Norwegian psychologist Dan Olweus describes "A student is bullied when aggressive actions are carried out against him during a period of time by one or more persons. The student is acutely experiencing aggression, but for various reasons cannot respond to it". Inequality of forces, repeatability and inadequately high sensitivity of the victim are essential signs of bullying. According to the majority of researchers, described in the Internet encyclopedia "Wikipedia", bullying includes four main components:

- this is aggressive and negative behavior;
- it is carried out regularly;
- it occurs in relationships where the participants have unequal power;
- this behavior is intentional.

Physical aggression: It includes pushing, shoving, kicking and hitting – it can also take the form of severe physical violence. In extreme cases, weapons, such as knives, can be used. This behavior is more common among boys than among girls.

Verbal bullying: In this case, the voice is the weapon. It can exist in the form of an offensive name (nickname), which is constantly addressed to one person, thereby injuring,

insulting and humiliating him. This type of bullying is often aimed at those victims who have noticeable differences in physical appearance, accent or voice characteristics and high or low academic performance.

Intimidation: Based on the use of very aggressive body language and voice intonation to force the victim to do what he/she does not want to do. A bully's facial expressions or "look" may express aggression and/or dislike. Threats are also used to undermine the victim's confidence.

Isolation: The initiator of using this method is usually a bully. The victim is intentionally isolated, expelled, or ignored by part of the class or the entire class. This may be accompanied by the distribution of notes, the whispering of insults that can be heard by the victim, or humiliating inscriptions on the board or in public places.

Extortion: In this case, money is demanded from the victim and threatened if he/she does not give it immediately. Breakfast, coupons or lunch money can also be extorted. The victim may also be forced to steal property for the bully. This tactic is used solely to place the blame on the victim.

Damage to property: The bully may focus on the victim's property. As a result, clothes, textbooks or other personal belongings may be damaged, stolen or hidden.

The specific forms and methods of bullying are constantly changing. Modern technologies create favorable opportunities for such negative phenomena as intimidation and bullying using the Internet, mobile phone and other technological resources. This phenomenon is much more dangerous than what we were dealing with only a generation ago. It was called "cyberbullying".

How can we find out that someone is being bullied?

Each drama assumes a clear distribution of roles. In a situation of harassment, there are always instigators, victims and, of course, persecutors — the bulk of children who, under the leadership of the instigators, carry out harassment. Sometimes there are also neutral observers in the class, who do not differ from the persecutors, since by their silence they encourage harassment without hindering it in any way.

It happens that there are defenders of the victim among classmates. Sometimes the appearance of a defender can radically change the situation (especially if there are several defenders or their opinion is taken into account in the class) — most persecutors leave the outcast alone, the conflict comes to naught at the very beginning. But, quite often the defender of the outcast himself becomes an outcast. For example, if, obeying the will of the teacher, a child is forced to sit at the same desk with an outcast, then, he may gradually become an object of ridicule, unless he begins to actively participate in the harassment of a neighbor on the desk.

The instigators. Usually one or two people in the class become the initiators of bullying. For some reason, they did not like someone from their classmates and they begin to tease him, bully, ridicule, defiantly avoid, not take him into games.

The process of rejection begins very early: already in the second or third quarter in the first grade, it becomes clear who has become an outcast, and who is the initiator of his harassment. Boys are the initiators of bullying both boys and girls, and girls most often attack girls (in the case of bullying a boy, they either simply share a common point of view, or even begin to defend the outcast).

Most often, the pursuit is based on the desire to assert oneself, to stand out. Very rarely, bullying is the result of personal revenge.

The famous Norwegian psychologist Dan Olweus noted their following typical traits, despite the fact that similar character traits can also occur in children who are not initiators of school bullying. What kind of children are they?

- These are children who are confident that "dominating" and subordinating, it will be much easier to achieve their goals;
- Those who do not know how to sympathize with their victims;
- Physically strong boys;
- Easily excitable and very impulsive, with aggressive behavior.
- Those who want to be the center of attention;
- Confident in their superiority over the victim;
- With a high level of pretension;
- Those who dream of being leaders in the classroom;
- Aggressive children who "need" a victim for their self-affirmation;
- Children who do not recognize compromises;
- With weak self-control;

Intuitively feeling which classmates will not resist them.

So, the initiators of bullying can be:

- active, sociable children who claim to be a leader in the classroom;
- aggressive children who have found an unrequited victim for self-affirmation;
- children who strive to be the center of attention at any cost;
- children who are used to treating others with a sense of superiority, dividing everyone into "their own" and "strangers";
- egocentric people who do not know how to sympathize with others, put themselves in the place of others;
- maximalists, unwilling to compromise children.

The pursuers. As already mentioned, several people become the instigators of harassment, all the others are their followers. They laugh with pleasure at the failures of the outcast, hide his things in the toilet, pick up offensive nicknames, do not miss the opportunity to push him, insult him or defiantly ignore and do not want to take him into their games. Why do kind and sympathetic children towards their loved ones become tyrants for a peer who has not done anything wrong to them personally?

Firstly, most of the pupils obey the so-called herd feeling: "Everyone went, and I went, everyone pushed, and I pushed." The child does not think about what is happening, he just participates in the general fun. It does not occur to him what the victim feels at this moment, how painful, insulting and scary he/she is.

Secondly, some do it in the hope of earning a class leader.

Thirdly, some people take part in bullying out of boredom, for fun (they will kick a ball or play tag with the same delight).

Fourth, some children actively persecute the outcast out of fear of being in the same position or simply do not dare to go against the majority.

Finally, a small percentage of pursuers thus assert themselves, take revenge for their failures in something. They lack the energy to become the instigators, but they willingly pick up someone else's initiative. Most often these are children who are bullied in the yard, offended by elders, severely punished by parents, they are unsuccessful in their studies and do not cause much sympathy among classmates.

What does our legislature say on bullying?

“Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan” Article 14. “Responsibility of minors for administrative offenses” says:

Persons aged sixteen to eighteen who have committed administrative offenses are subject to the measures provided for by the Regulations on Interdepartmental Commissions on Juvenile Affairs.

Article 183. “Petty hooliganism” says:

Petty hooliganism, that is, deliberate disregard for the rules of conduct in society, expressed in obscene language in public places, insulting harassment of citizens and other similar actions that violate public order and peace of citizens, – entails the imposition of a fine from three to five basic settlement units or administrative arrest up to fifteen days.

Also, in some cases, the measures provided for in the regulation on interdepartmental commissions for minors are applied to them.

Impact measures used by the commissions:

- 1) oblige the minor to apologize to the victim;
- 2) to warn;
- 3) impose on a minor who has reached the age of fifteen, if he has an independent wage, and if the amount of the damage does not exceed the specified minimum monthly wage, to impose the obligation to compensate for the material damage caused or to eliminate it, or submit a submission to the district (city) court on imposing the obligation to compensate material damage with one's own labor, which does not exceed the specified minimum monthly salary;
- 4) to impose a fine on a minor who has reached the age of sixteen and has an independent salary in the cases and amounts provided for in the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 5) transfer the minor to the supervision of his parents or their substitutes or public educators, as well as to the supervision of the labor team or non-governmental non-profit organization with their consent;
- 6) send a request to the court to place a minor in a specialized educational institution in the cases and in the order provided for by law.

What can a teacher do he/she you think that a pupil is being bullied

If a pupil does not want to talk openly about being bullied, but a teacher is concerned about his/her behavior or information a teacher has heard from others, first of all the teacher should try to talk to him/her. At first, he/she may avoid talking, believing that the teacher will not understand anything anyway. Nevertheless, teachers should let him/her know that teachers are always ready to listen to pupils, and give them the opportunity to choose the moment himself.

Alternatively, teachers can contact another adult or a trusted person with whom it will be easier for that pupil to talk. Teachers should be glad that there is a person whom the pupil trusts.

If he/she stubbornly does not want to share his/her trouble with any of his/her relatives and friends, it is worth seeking help from school psychologist.

It is important for the teacher not to look for the instigators or pursuers, but to focus on helping the victim of bullying. Help children take care of the victim. An organized meeting of the abusers and a few more people who take a neutral position will help. It is important to explain to the pupils what the victim feels. Teacher should ask them to suggest options and solutions that will alleviate the suffering of the affected pupil. By joining the "project" and feeling their importance, classmates will be able to help.

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